

Striped individuals of the grass snake, *Natrix natrix* (Linnaeus, 1758) in anthropogenic habitats of Berlin, Germany, might indicate human introduction

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Abstract. We report three recent observations of striped individuals of the grass snake (*Natrix natrix*) from Berlin, Germany. Such animals have been described from the region earlier, although this color morph is typical for south-eastern European populations. All three observations were made in anthropogenic habitats, which have been highly frequented by visitors for decades. Based on our anecdotal findings and recent publications on the morpho-geography of the species, we hypothesize that introduced individuals might play a more significant role in the polymorphism of grass snakes than previously thought. Finally, we overview all published observations of striped grass snakes in Central Europe and discuss the implications of potentially introduced non-native genotypes.

Keywords: anthropogenic habitat, Colubridae, Europe, introduction, Natricinae, reptile, Squamata, urban ecology.

The grass snake *Natrix natrix* (Linnaeus 1758) is the most common snake species in Germany and its capital, Berlin (Kühnel et al. 2017). While it was formerly believed that this species occurs from Northwestern Africa and the Iberian Peninsula to Lake Baikal, today three species of grass snakes are recognized, *N. astreptophora* from Northwestern Africa and the Iberian Peninsula and adjacent France, *N. helvetica* from Western Europe, and *N. natrix* sensu stricto occurring from Central Europe and Fennoscandia eastward to Lake Baikal (Pokrant et al. 2016, Kindler et al. 2017). Within *N. natrix*, four genetically distinct subspecies are accepted, which are admix in contact zones (Asztalos et al. 2021a). Even though these subspecies show considerable variation in coloration and pattern, Fritz & Ihlow (2022) revealed subspecies-specific differences in coloration and pattern using a large Citizen Science dataset from iNaturalist. In Germany, there are two subspecies, namely *N. n. natrix* in the north of the country and *N. n. vulgaris* in the south. Following Fritz & Ihlow (2022), the nominotypical subspecies is uniformly grey to greyish brown colored, without stripes on the back. *Natrix natrix vulgaris* tends to be lighter in body coloration and shows occasionally slight dorsal stripes (Fritz & Ihlow 2022). Pronounced, light back stripes are present in many representatives of the subspecies *N. n. moreotica* from the southern Balkans. While *N. n. natrix* is distributed over central to northern Germany and Scandinavia, *N. n. vulgaris* is currently only known from south Central Europe, including southern Germany, Hungary, and Austria (Kindler et al. 2017, Schultze et al. 2019, Fritz & Schmidler 2020, Asztalos et al. 2021a). The contact zone of both subspecies extends over large areas of central-eastern Europe and reaches eastern Germany. The city of Berlin is located right on the edge of the contact zone (Asztalos et al. 2021a). However, striped grass snakes should not occur in this area.

Nevertheless, striped grass snakes are regularly reported from Berlin (Günther & Völkl 1996) as well as from other German cities, like Dresden, Leipzig, and Stuttgart (Grosse 1995, Günther & Völkl 1996, Grosse 2011, Arnold 2015, Fritz et al. 2023). Such individuals were formerly considered as natural rare exceptions (Günther & Völkl 1996), while Fritz &

Ihlow (2022) suggested that they rather represent introduced snakes. Non-native striped *N. natrix* are also known from Switzerland (Dubey et al. 2017) and the Netherlands (Asztalos et al. 2021b). An overview of the mentioned reports is presented in Figure 1. In the current study, we report three recent observations made in Berlin.

All observations were made during guided tours or nature education events in Berlin. Exact locations are given below, together with descriptions of the encounters. Photos were taken with a Canon EOS R camera (60mm macro lens) or an iPhone 12. The map was created with QGIS 3.32.3, and all photos were edited with Adobe Lightroom Classic 13.0.1. On 11 June 2022, around 09:30 in the morning (local time), the two authors spotted a female grass snake of approximately 70 cm total length basking on a *Picea* bush (Fig. 2B), around 1m above the ground in a large park in Berlin-Britz (52.432176N, 13.415208E). Sex was determined by tail length and body proportions, and palpation indicated that the animal was gravid. In the cultivated garden area, the snake was found close to an artificial 7x1m pond with walled banks, in which calling *Pelophylax* kl. *esculentus* and tadpoles were present. The snake had a chocolate brown coloration with two light dorsolateral stripes and two dorsal lines of dark spots. Dark spots formed black bars on the flanks, and the lunar stains were creme-colored (Fig. 2B, C). The snake was carefully captured to take proper photographs of the coloration and released in the same bush right afterward. It was seen again basking at the same spot the next day.

On the 9th of May 2023, around 16:00 (local time), an assumed male (determined by the tail length and body proportions) *N. natrix* of approximately 45 cm total length was found moving on the banks of an artificial pond in a fenced area in Berlin-Treptow (52.485563N, 13.491479E). This individual had a light olive-brown coloration with two very bright dorsolateral stripes. Tiny dark spots along these lines were visible, and the lunar stains were intensely orange (Fig. 3B). Due to the interesting pattern, the snake was caught to take photos and set free at the same spot directly after. The same, or a very similar individual (based on dorsal coloration) was seen again around two months later at the same location.

On the 15th of June 2023, around 19:00 (local time), five hatchlings of *N. natrix* were found under a stone close to an artificial pond (52.486182N, 13.489912E) in the same fenced area of Berlin-Treptow. All individuals were around 20 cm in total length. One of them had a slightly striped pattern. The

dorsolateral stripes were dull and a little brighter than the greyish-brown body color, with dark spots along the back and flanks (Fig. 3C). All five individuals were released under the same stone a few minutes after collecting the data and taking pictures.

Figure 1. Map of published findings of striped *N. natrix* (or their hybrid offspring) in central Europe. White circles = former records from literature, and black triangles = new finding locations, as mentioned herein. 1) Günther and Völkl (1996); 2) Grosse (1995, 2009, 2011); 3) Dubey et al. (2017); 4) Asztalos et al. (2021a); 5) Fritz et al. (2023); 6) new findings of this article.

Figure 2. Photographs of the observation at "Britzer Garten". Picea bush (A) in which the animal was found, close-up of the bush with the grass Snake in situ (B). Portrait of the individual (C) with well-visible dorsolateral stripes and black spots on the back and flanks.

Figure 3. Observations at "Spreepark". Artificial pond (A) where the first individual was found. The first individual in dorsal view (B) with well-visible orange lunar stains and bright yellowish dorsolateral lines. One of the five hatchlings (C), found a month later nearby, showed a similar, less striking pattern.

We described three encounters of striped grass snakes from Berlin, where this species is usually uniformly grey or greyish brown without stripes (Fritz & Ihlow 2022).

The three striped grass snakes from Berlin contrast the more than 100 individuals of *N. natrix* the authors have observed in and around Berlin, all of which had the characteristic of *N. n. natrix* uniformly grey or greyish brown color pattern without stripes (Fritz & Ihlow 2022). Fritz & Ihlow (2022) did not report a single striped *N. natrix* among 752 observations on iNaturalist for Germany. A year later, there were two findings on the platform, one of which is the herein-described finding from "Britzer Garten" (Fritz et al. 2023). Although oddly colored grass snakes are occasionally found all over their distribution range (Bjelica & Anđelković 2021, Griesbaum 2022, Jablonski et al. 2022), the local accumulation, especially in two anthropogenic habitats, might indicate human involvement.

The fenced park "Britzer Garten" is a former fallow land transformed into an artificial landscape, including small lakes and different botanical exhibits for the National Garden Exhibition in 1985 (Grün Berlin 2023). Since 1989, the venue has been open to the public in the daytime but closed at night. Therefore, many thousands of visitors frequent the area every year. The second site, the "Spreepark", is a former amusement park whose area was largely sealed during the German Democratic Republic (GDR). After reunification, the park was further developed, and the area was diversely designed with water bodies and changing topography between the funfair rides. The park has been closed since 2001, and after remaining in its fallow for a long time, it is currently being converted back into a public park (Busch et al. 2017).

Urban areas, in general, are well known to play a key role in the human-induced introduction of non-native organisms around the globe due to their nature as a hub for travel and transportation (Abellán et al. 2016, Faulkner et al. 2016). On a habitat scale, the spatial proximity to anthropogenic structures such as housing or streets has further been identified as a reliable predictor for non-native taxa (Trombulak & Frissell 2000). For instance, Copp et al. (2005) showed a clear positive relationship between the occurrence of ornamental freshwater fish and the distance to the nearest road or footpath in urban ponds. The authors linked the abundance of introduced fish species in more urban environments to a higher probability of introducing events through residents. As both sites in which the here-described striped grass snakes were found are (or have been in the past) characterized by a high level of accessibility for the public, we hypothesize that the presence of the observed untypical *N. natrix* individuals might be a result of introduction event.

Human introductions of alien grass snake species or subspecies have been proven several times in Europe, either by accident (Dubey et al. 2017, Ahnelt et al. 2021) or intentionally (Grosse 2011, Asztalos et al. 2021b). These findings, combined with additional evidence from a study on the species color pattern by Fritz & Ihlow (2022), suggest that striped individuals of grass snakes in large cities of Central Europe might trace back to introduced individuals.

Both adult individuals described in the current study highly resemble animals assigned to *N. n. moreotica*, which occurs in south-eastern Europe (Fritz & Ihlow 2022, Asztalos et al. 2021a). Furthermore, the first individual (Fig. 1) looks

almost identical to a specimen from southern Bulgaria (hence pure *N. n. moreotica* region) depicted by Asztalos et al. (2021a). Considering the similarities mentioned, we hypothesize that the individuals described here might be direct descendants of individuals introduced from the Balkans. This theory is supported by the fact that thousands of reptiles were collected from that area for the pet trade in the mid-20th century (Mertens 1960, Spellerberg 1976). Furthermore, this area was and still is one of the favorite holiday destinations for Germans and one of the only destinations for citizens of the former German Democratic Republic (GDR). During that time, many terrarists also took self-caught animals home from vacations. A release of Balkans-originating grass snakes in 1964 has already been proven for Leipzig, a large city of the former GDR (Grosse 2009). In addition, construction material was and still is imported to Germany from eastern European countries. For the island of Sylt, cases of accidental introductions of vipers (*Vipera berus* (Linnaeus, 1758)) and a dice snake (*Natrix tessellata* (Laurenti, 1768)) with shipments of reed, fascine material or peat (Grosse et al. 2006, Grosse 2012) have been reported. Also, Böhme and Grell (2013) and Ahnelt et al. (2021) suppose that the founder individuals of *N. natrix* on Sylt originate from shipments of reed and fascine material. However, molecular studies incorporating DNA sampling are needed to confirm if the individuals reported in the current study are descendants of grass snakes introduced from the Balkans.

As all three here described individuals were either in a substantially different age class or found in clearly distinct urban areas, we confidently rule out the possibility of recording the same animal twice. Moreover, the different reproductive states of the individuals (gravid female, sexually mature male, hatchling) suggest that the genotype, which produces striped individuals, already might have spread among the local populations. This suggestion is well in line with the findings of Asztalos et al. (2021b), which identify hybridization between *N. natrix* and *N. helvetica* as a cause for regional phenotypic variation in grass snake populations in the Netherlands. Even if releases of south-eastern European grass snakes have occurred in the past in Berlin, the striped individuals and their potential hybrid descendants are still scarce. However, the hatchling we found might indicate a possible intermediate phenotype resulting from direct crossbreeding with local *N. n. natrix*. This would mean that individuals with small genetic remains of a former hybridization could be difficult (if at all) to recognize today without molecular confirmation. Future molecular studies are, therefore, an essential tool to test for the potential spreading of *N. n. moreotica* genome fragments around Berlin.

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